

LEARNING OUTSIDE THE CLASSROOM: EFFECTS OF PRINCIPAL'S LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOR IN THE PREPARATION OF INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERS

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ABSTRACT

The essence of organizational leadership is to coordinate and facilitate the efforts of individuals and organizations to achieve common goals. By shaping the process of determining success, leaders can improve the performance of their teams and organizations. An essential goal of most leadership studies was for teams to recognize behavioral aspects that clarify the influence of leaders on the success of a unit of work or organization. The purpose of this study was to find out how principal's leadership behavior affects teachers learning outcomes in the preparation of instructional leaders in public schools in the division of San Pablo City. A descriptive survey research design was used with a researcher-made survey questionnaire in google form distributed among 570 teachers at the secondary level. Frequency, percent, mean, standard deviation, and regression analysis were employed to analyze the data. The results show a significant relationship between the perceived principal's leadership behavior and the teachers' well-being and performances. Likewise, there is a single or combination of two variables from the principal's leadership behavior that directly affect teachers' well-being and performances to increase their motivation and engagement to become instructional leaders. The researcher assumes that the positive behavior of the school principals provides a great help in improving teacher's learning outcomes. The study recommends that the school principal may establish relationships that are time-tested and solid, supporting professional development, sincere, and recognizing the value of building trust with their teachers to make them feel fairness and prestige in the school. Teachers may be encouraged to support and provide quality education to increase student's performances and school effectiveness.

Keywords: Principal's leadership behavior; instructional leaders; teachers well-being, performances; learning outcomes